

THE PREVALENCE AND PATTERNS OF IMPAIRED LUNG FUNCTION IN IRAQI PATIENTS WITH TYPE II DIABETES MELLITUS**Mohammed Waleed Sayyid Ghany,***Senior of Internal medicine specialist, A physician specializing / Interventional Cardiology, Medical City-Iraqi Center for Heart Disease***Omar Farooq Al-Azzawi***Professor of Internal Medicine, Medical College/University of Baghdad, Consultant Physician, Department of Internal Medicine, Baghdad Teaching Hospital/Medical City***Abstract**

Background: *Diabetes mellitus* (DM) refers to a group of metabolic disorders that share the phenotype of chronic hyperglycemia, leading to chronic macrovascular and microvascular complications if not managed properly. Among these complications, lung involvement has been poorly characterized and followed worldwide, although the lung is a major organ in the body, same as other organs that are affected by microvascular and macrovascular complications. **Aim of study:** To determine the prevalence and patterns of impaired lung function in Iraqi patients with type II DM. **Patients and methods:** This cross-sectional study included (100) patients with II diabetes who were visiting Baghdad teaching hospital during the period from August 2014 to March 2015 for follow up. The patients accepted to take part in this study, after fulfilling the exclusion and inclusion criteria. The pulmonary function test was carried out using the Spirometer according to standard guidelines. **Results:** The results showed that 58 (58%) of type II DM patients had impaired pulmonary function, 38 (38%) had restrictive defect. Other impaired pulmonary functions showed that obstructive pattern constituted (13%) and mixed pattern constituted (7%) of the patients. **Conclusions:** Type II *Diabetes mellitus* can adversely affect and impair pulmonary function, this impairment, predominantly show restrictive pattern of airway disease, in addition to other less common patterns of involvement.

Keywords: Type II diabetes, Impaired lung function, Prevalence, Patterns.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) refers to a group of common metabolic disorders that share the phenotype of hyperglycemia. Several distinct types of DM are identified and are caused by a complex, genetic and environmental factors. Depending on the etiology of DM, factors contributing to hyperglycemia include: Reduced insulin secretion, decreased glucose utilization and increased glucose production [1].

Diabetes mellitus is classified on the basis of the pathogenic process that leads to hyperglycemia into: Type I DM, which is the result of complete or near-total insulin deficiency, type II DM, which is a heterogeneous group of disorders characterized by variable degrees of insulin resistance, impaired insulin secretion, and increased glucose production. Other etiologies for DM include gestational DM and secondary causes of DM such as pancreatitis, pancreatectomy, acromegaly, Cushing's syndrome, glucocorticoids and infections such congenital rubella, cytomegalovirus, coxsackie virus [1].

The incidence of DM is increasing and is becoming a global epidemic due to population growth, aging, urbanization, increasing prevalence of obesity and physical inactivity. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) has subsequently released estimates of the numbers of people with diabetes for 2003 and forecasts for 2025 of 194 million and 334 million, respectively [2].

One of the main problems facing patients with DM in addition to the problems of adhering to a daily healthy life style and compliance with treatment, are the well-known chronic complications of DM, especially if it was not managed properly. These complications are

classified into (1): Microvascular complications (neuropathy, nephropathy and retinopathy) and (2): Macrovascular complications (coronary artery disease, cerebrovascular accidents and peripheral vascular disease) [1,3]

Lung involvement in diabetes mellitus (the subject of our study) has been poorly characterized and followed worldwide [4]. While it is known that persons with DM are at increased risk of pulmonary infections, bronchiectasis and abscesses [5,6], several outcomes has been described regarding the pulmonary function [7].

Pulmonary diabetic microangiopathy usually remains under-recognized [5], and pulmonary damage in most patients with DM is subclinical and rarely present as a complaint [8]. Reduced antioxidant defense of the lung and immune function impairment is another causative factor that reduces lung function [9, 10].

Respiratory muscle weakness reduces inspiratory and expiratory capacity and this decreases the vital capacity. So, measurement of FVC is an excellent mean of detecting respiratory muscle weakness [11].

Patients and methods

This cross-sectional study included (100) patients with II diabetes who were visiting Baghdad teaching hospital during the period from August 2014 to March 2015 for follow up. The patients accepted to take part in this study, after fulfilling the exclusion and inclusion criteria. The pulmonary function test was carried out using the Spirometer according to standard guidelines.

Complete physical examination especially of the respiratory, cardiovascular and skeletal system was performed to help in the exclusion of patients with acute and/or chronic respiratory disease.

Diabetes mellitus type II patients included were previously diagnosed and confirmed by HbA1C, and already treated by oral antidiabetic agents.

Patients with history of acute or chronic respiratory infections, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), heart failure were excluded from the study. Subjects with history of smoking, neuromuscular diseases, and those who had undergone chest surgery or other major operations, and patients with gross abnormalities of the thoracic cage were also excluded from the study, while all other patients with type II DM without the above conditions were included.

Pulmonary function test was done by a trained spirometrist using a master lab (made in Germany). The Forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV1), forced vital capacity (FVC), and ratio of FEV1/FVC were measured.

The results were given in liters and compared to the predicted values of patients themselves, using the European thoracic standardization of spirometry. All measurements were made in an upright sitting position with nose clips. The patients held the mouth piece that is attached to the spirometer, (avoiding the tongue) in the mouth tightly to prevent leakage of air. Then the patients were instructed to inspire maximally and after that, to expire forcefully at once through the mouth piece into the spirometer.

The best of three acceptable measurements were taken. The outcomes of the test were classified as

- Normal if FEV1/FVC was greater than 70%.
- Obstructive ventilatory defect if FEV1/FVC was less than 70%.
- Restrictive ventilatory defect if the ratio of FEV1/FVC was greater than 70%, and the ratio of obtained FVC / predicted FVC less than 80%.
- Mixed ventilatory defect if FEV1/FVC was less than 70%, and the ratio of obtained FVC to predicted FVC was less than 80% [10,12].

Statistical analysis

Statistical package for social science version 20 (SPSS-20) was used for data analysis. Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm SD and discrete variable was presented as number and percentage. The T-test for independence was used to test the significance between continuous variables. Binary logistic regression analysis was used to predict certain variables. P-value of (<0.05) was considered significant.

Results

In the current study, 100 patients with type II diabetes were studied. Results in table (1) showed that the mean FEV1 in diabetic patients was significantly lower than the predicted FEV1 values ($p=0.001$), and the mean FVC in diabetic patients was lower than the predicted FVC ($p=0.001$).

Table (1)

Pulmonary function test values of patients and predicted

Variables		N	Mean	SD	p-value
FEV1	Patient	100	2.19	0.75	0.0001
	Predicted	100	2.76	0.72	
FVC	Patient	100	2.73	1.12	0.0001
	Predicted	100	3.35	0.853	

Total prevalence of impaired pulmonary function test in patient with type II DM was 58%. Restrictive pattern was shown in 38% of them, 13% had obstructive pattern, while 7% had mixed type as illustrated in table (2).

Table (2)

Prevalence of normal and impaired pulmonary function test

Prevalence according to pattern		percent	Total percent
Impaired PFT	Restrictive	38%	58%
	Obstructive	13%	
	Mixed	7%	
Normal PFT			42%

The dominant effect of type II DM on pulmonary dysfunction was the restrictive pattern of involvement of different degrees:

1- 20 (52.6%) of the patients with restrictive lung involvement was of amild severity, their FVC was between 65%-80% of the predicted according to American Thoracic Association (ATS).

2- 13 (34.2%) of the patients with restrictive lung involvement was of amoderate severity, and their FVC was between 50-65% of the predicted according to ATS.

3- 5 (13.2%) of the patients with restrictive lung involvement was of asevere form, and their FVC was less than 50% according to ATS as shown in table (3).

Table (3)

Degree of severity of restrictive pulmonary function

Variable	Frequency	Percent	
Severity of restrictive lung disease	Mild	20	52%
	Moderate	13	34.2%
	Severe	5	13.2%
	Total	38	100%

Discussion

Only few studies were made focusing on the association between diabetes and abnormal pulmonary function test, particularly in the middle east and especially in Iraq [13].

In this study, type II diabetes was associated with impairment of pulmonary function in the form of a significant reduction in FEV1 and FVC and a significant increase in FEV1/FVC ratio, compared with their matched predicted values.

The most obvious effect of type II DM on pulmonary function is in the form of restrictive pattern which is mainly due to non-enzymatic glycosylation of the lung which is rich in collagen and elastin, that may lead to stiffening of the thorax and lung parenchyma [14].

Obstructive impairment in patients with diabetes is related to the presence of systemic inflammation and is associated with endothelial dysfunction that in addition, it may contribute independently to airflow obstruction [15].

Previous studies that were done in Iraq, [13] concentrated only on the effect of type II DM on lung function, not the prevalence, They found that the main impairment of the pulmonary function in type II DM was also the restrictive pattern, similar to our results, they also found that the involvement was related to the duration of DM and glycemic control but those studies involved only a small number of patients, and did not show the prevalence nor the patterns of lung dysfunction.

The results of our study are generally consistent with the results of these studies which demonstrated abnormal pulmonary function tests in adults with type II diabetes mellitus.

Yeh *et al.*, [16] conducted a cross-sectional and prospective study using basal and 3 years follow up data of 1000 type II diabetic patients and 10162 non-diabetic adults from the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities (ARIC) study. At baseline, they found that type II diabetes patients had significantly lower FEV1 and FVC and significantly higher FEV1/FVC ratio than their non-diabetic counterparts. With follow up they found that FEV1 and FVC declined faster in type II diabetic patients than non-diabetic subjects.

Adeyeye *et al.*, Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Nigeria [17] conducted a cross-sectional study using two hundred persons with type II DM [17&18]. They found that restrictive lung dysfunction is the predominant abnormality of pulmonary dysfunction in persons with type II DM, with a prevalence of 38%. They also found that 11% of the patients had obstructive pattern and 8% mixed type, while the patients with normal PFT were 43% and this was quite similar to the results of our study.

Zainab Abdulridha Akber *et al.*, [13] conducted a cross-sectional study of 63 type II DM in the department of Physiology, College of Medicine, University of Basra, /Iraq. They found that type II diabetes adversely affects pulmonary function, and this impairment shows restrictive pattern mainly, similar to the results of our study, although they did not detect other patterns of involvement as in our study, they concen-

trated on the effect of airway disease, graded by the duration of diabetes, level of fasting blood sugar, and type of diabetes treatment.

In Saudi Arabia, Meo *et al.*, [6] performed a case control study on 32 men with type II diabetes and 40 non-diabetic controls, they found that diabetes patients had lower FEV1 and FVC relative to non-diabetic controls and this reduction was proportional to the duration of diabetes, but they failed to demonstrate a significant change in FEV1/FVC ratio.

All of these studies in spite of their different aims and methodology agree that patients with DM are at high risk of lung involvement, mainly of the restrictive type, as a complication, whether due to microangiopathy, inflammatory or reduced antioxidant defense.

References

1. Fauci AS, Kasper DL, Longo DL, Braunwald E, Hauser SL, Jameson JL, et al. Diabetes Mellitus. Harrison's principals of Internal Medicine. (19th edition) 2015;2399-2400.
2. International Diabetes Federation: Diabetes Atlas 2003. Brussels, International Diabetes Federation, 2003.
3. King H, Aubert RE, Herman WH; Global burden of diabetes; 1995-2025 Prevalence, Numerical estimates and projections, Diabetes Care, 1998;21(9): 1414-1431.
4. Davis WA, Knuiman M, Kendall P, Grange V, Davis TM (2004) Glycemic exposure is associated with reduced pulmonary function in type 2 diabetes: the free mantle Diabetes study. Diabetes care 27: 338-43.
5. Sandler M (1990) Is the lung a target organ in diabetes mellitus? Arch intern Med 1507: 1385-1388.
6. Meo SA, Al-ezees AM, Arif M, Al-Rubean K (2006) Lung function in type 2 Saudi diabetic patients. Saudi Med J 27: 338-343.
7. A Kaparianos, E Argyropoulou, F Sampsonas. Chronic Respir Dis 2008; 5:101-108.
8. Walter R, Beiser A, Givelber R; The association between glycemic state and lung function: the Framingham heart study. Am J Respir Crit Care Med., 2003; 167: 911-916.
9. Weynand B, Jonckheere A, Frans A, Rahier J; Diabetes mellitus induces a thickening of the pulmonary basal lamina. Respiration, 1999; 66(1): 14-19.
10. American Thoracic Society – Standardization of spirometry 1995 update. Am J respire Crit Care Med. 1995; 152:1107-36. [PubMed].
11. Nathan DM, Genuth S, Lachin J, Cleary P, Crofford O, Davis M. Diabetes Control and Complications Trial Research Group. The effect of intensive treatment of diabetes on the development and progression of long-term complications in insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. N Engl J Med. 1993 30;329(14):977-86. PMID: 8366922. N Eng J Med; 329:977-986.
12. Brian R. Walker, Nicki R. Colledge, Stuart H. ralston; Davidsons Principles and Practice of Medicine 2014, 22th edition.
13. Zainab Abdulridha Akber*, Nabeel I. AL-Edani*, Layla Othman Khalid*. Pulmonary Function in Type 2 Diabetic Patients in Basrah, The N Iraqi J Med,

April 2013;9(1):76-81.

14. Davis WA, Knudman M, Kendall P, Grange V, Davis TM. Glycemic exposure is associated with reduced pulmonary function in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2004;27:752-757.

15. Michael David Goldman, Lung Dysfunction in Diabetes, American diabetic association, Diabetic care October 2014.

16. Yeh HC, Punjabi NM, Wang NY, Pankow J, Duncan BB, Cox CE, et al. Cross-sectional and prospective study in adults with type 2 diabetes: The Ath-

erosclerosis Risk In Communities (ARIC) study. *Diabetes Care* 2008;31:741-746.

17. Adeyeye OO*, Ogbera OA, Dada AO, Bamisile RT and Brodie Mens A, Correlates of Abnormal Pulmonary Function Tests in Persons with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, *J Pulm Respir. Med* 2014, 5:1, Volume 5 • Issue 1 •1000231.

18. Tektook, N. Kh, Threaf, M.,F., Eptissam Younan Pirko, E. Y., Helicobacter pylori Infected in Iraqi diabetic Patients (Type 2) and its Correlated with level of Proinflammatory Cytokine, *Research J. Pharm. and Tech.* 2019; 12(9):4255-4258.